

**DIGITALISED FINANCIAL INCLUSION IN INDIA: THE PATH
TOWARDS DIGITALLY AND FINANCIALLY EMPOWERED ECONOMY**

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Abstract

Digitalized financial inclusion is one of the innovative and effective mechanisms which help to provide financial services to unreached and uncovered people in India. Providing financial services to the underprivileged people is a part of financial system of the country that promotes socio economic development. Therefore, there is a need of understanding the impact of digitalized financial inclusion in India with respect to the application of modern communication technology. As of 31 December 2018, India had a population of 130 crore people, 123 crore [Aadhaar](#) digital biometric identity cards, 121 crore mobile phones, 44.6 crore smartphones, 560 million internet users up from 481 million users (2017) and 51 per cent growth in e-commerce. The cash payments are still most popular means of payment for about 67% of the country's population. Only 10% of Indian population uses debit or credit cards and money transfer via expensive and informal channel such as hawalas is common. In this context, the innovative DFS (Digitalized Financial Services) needs to be adopted as a big opportunity to realize digitalized financial inclusion. By 2020, it is estimated that the mobile will have the potential to serve about 250 million people for financial services in India. In order to transform the entire ecosystem of public services through the use of information technology, making financial transactions electronic & cashless, enabling citizen participation in digital & financial space with the help of mobile phone and bank accounts, the Government of India and Central bank are striving to take the nation forward – Digitally, Financially and Economically.

Keywords: Digital Payment, Financial Inclusion, Digitalized Financial Inclusion, DFS, Empowerment, E-Commerce.

INTRODUCTION

Financial inclusion is one of the most essential parameters of economic development, which also assists in the poverty reduction and can act as a way to prevent social exclusion (Aaluri et al., 2016). The financial inclusion can be improved using Digital Financial Services (DFS), which has been attributed as one of the key financial solutions. Digital financial inclusion is one of the innovative and effective mechanisms which help to provide financial services to unreached and uncovered people in the country.

Digital Financial Services refer to very broad spectrum of financial services accessed and delivered through digital channels, including payments, credit, savings, remittances, insurance and financial information. The term “digital channels” refers to the internet, mobile phones (both smart phones and digital feature phones), ATMs, POS terminals, NFC-enabled devices, chips, electronically enabled cards, biometric devices, tablets and any other digital system (AFI, 2016). DFS have significant potential to expand the delivery of basic financial services via affordable, convenient and secure environment to the public at large (particularly the poor) through innovative technologies like mobile-phone-enabled solutions, electronic money models, and digital payment platforms. Financial Institutions (Banks, Micro-finance institutions) and non-Financial firms (mobile network operators) and third-party providers (agent network managers, payment aggregators, and others) are leveraging digital channels to offer basic financial services at greater convenience, scale and lower cost than traditional banking allow. The population of India is more than 1.324 billion (2016) of which 60% people are under-banked, while as many of 75% possess the mobile phones. The cash payments are still most popular means of payment for about 67% of the country’s population. Only 10% of Indian population uses debit or credit cards and money transfer via expensive and informal channel such as hawalas is common. In this context, the innovative DFS needs to be adopted as a big opportunity to realize financial inclusion. By 2020, it is estimated that the mobile will have the potential to serve about 250 million people for financial services in India.

DIGITAL FINANCIAL INCLUSION

Digital financial inclusion can be defined as digital access to and use of formal financial services by excluded and underserved populations. Such services should be suited to the customer’s needs and delivered responsibly, at a cost both affordable to customers and sustainable for providers. So, the main motive of digital financial inclusion initiative is to provide infrastructure and electronic services on demand. This initiative will surely increase the speed of financial inclusion. Therefore, there is a need of understanding the impact of financial inclusion in India with respect to the application of modern communication technology.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

(Istanbul, 2018) opine that Digital finance providers can use their discretion to pursue strategies that enrich welfare-maximizing digital finance services. Digital finance providers can make huge profits to increase their non-salary income for the services they offer. For instance, banks, non-bank financial institutions and Fintech firms (not the World Bank) are leading the push for digital financial inclusion in a bid to reach billions of new customers by offering digital financial services to the mobile (and digital) device of the excluded and underserved population in exchange for a fee. This will raise questions about banks and Fintech providers profiting from the poor, and also raise questions about how digital finance can lead to greater financial inclusion for individuals outside the formal sector and for individuals who deliberately refuse to use digital devices for financial transactions.

(Gabor & Brooks, 2017) examine the growing importance of digital-based financial inclusion as a form of organizing development interventions through networks of state institutions, international development organizations, philanthropic investment and fintech companies. The fintech-philanthropy-development (FPD) complex generates digital ecosystems that map, expand and monetize digital footprints. Its 'know thy (irrational) customer' vision combines behavioral economics with predictive algorithms to accelerate access to, and monitor engagement with, finance. The digital revolution adds new layers to the material cultures of financial(ised) inclusion, offering the state new ways of expanding the inclusion of the 'legible', and global finance new forms of 'profiling' poor households into generators of financial assets.

(Mader, 2016) has analyzed the turn toward financial inclusion in general, and digital money and the end of cash in particular, in development policy. It begins with a discussion of why financial inclusion has displaced microfinance on global development agendas, and has introduced new practices and players to the space of poverty finance. It shows how financial inclusion brings a modified theory of change, with financial intermediation rather than income generation now being seen as crucial to poverty alleviation, and explains the particular emphasis on promoting cashless payment systems in the name of inclusion. As becomes evident, powerful actor coalitions (card crusaders) seek the end of cash and the full digitalization of poor people's money in pursuit of three holy grails: to capitalize on everyday transaction costs, to seek and analyze big data generated by the poor, and to exert greater governmental power over poor people's money.

(Onaolapo, 2015) studied the effects of Financial Inclusion on the economic growth of Nigeria. He found a significant positive relationship between financial inclusion and economic growth. The author also showed that Financial Inclusion greatly influenced poverty reduction and financial intermediation through positively impacted Bank Branch Networks, Loans to Rural Areas and small enterprises.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The poor stay poor, not because they are lazy, but because they have no access to capital. Till date, a huge section of population remains outside the formal banking system. Financial Inclusion is an umbrella platform to reach the unbanked masses and make financial services accessible to them. Digital financial inclusion is one of the innovative and effective mechanisms which help to provide financial services with the help of modern ICT methods to unreached and uncovered people in the country. Providing financial services to the needy people is a part of financial system of the country that promotes socio economic development. Over the last few years the inclusive financial system has paved the ways in changing people lives and revitalizing communities. Hence it is appropriate and topical to focus the attention as to how the digital financial inclusion programs have made an upsurge in credit off-take for the upliftment of digital and financial empowerment of India. This study therefore intends to explore the DFS and digital financial inclusion for digital and financial empowerment of economy.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To understand the usage of mobiles and internet in the urban and rural areas.
- To highlight the initiatives taken by banks for promoting Digital Financial Services.
- To link digital empowerment with the philosophy and practice of inclusive growth.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This paper is exploratory in nature aimed at evaluating the initiatives taken by the selected Indian Banks with regard to the delivery of ICT based financial services. Study is based on secondary data published by RBI, Government departments, different agencies, research papers, journals, magazines, and news articles.

1)To understand the usage of mobiles and internet in the urban and rural areas.

Table-1: Overall Subscriber base and Tele-density as on March 31st 2018.

TELECOM REGULATORY AUTHORITY OF INDIA

New Delhi, March 31st 2018 (www.trai.gov.in)

Particulars	Wireless	Wireline	Total = Wireless+ Wireline
Total Subscribers (Million)	1183.41	22.81	1206.22
Urban Subscribers (Million)	662.18	19.43	681.61
Rural Subscribers (Million)	521.23	3.38	524.61
Overall Tele-density	91.09	1.76	92.84
Urban Tele-density	161.17	4.73	165.90
Rural Tele-density	58.67	0.38	59.05
Share of Urban Subscribers	55.96%	85.19%	56.51%
Share of Rural Subscribers	44.04%	14.81%	43.49%
No. of Broadband Subscribers (Million)	394.65	17.95	412.60

The growth trend in the Telecom Sector continued in 2017-18 also assisted with timely regulatory interventions of TRAI. The sector witnessed a substantial increase in the number of subscribers during the year. At the end of financial year 2017-18, the overall telecom subscriber base

has increased to 1206.22 million as compared to 1194.58 million at the end of financial year 2016-17 registering an increase of 11.64 million subscribers. The overall subscriber base and tele-density is depicted in the above table. The wireless subscriber base was 1183.41 million as on 31st March 2018 in comparison to the subscriber base of 1170.18 million as on 31st March 2017 registering a growth rate of 1.13% during the financial year 2017-18.

Table 2: The network operators in India and their subscription percentage.

(Subscriber base in million)

Service Providers	2016-17	2017-18	Percentage growth
Bharti	273.65	304.19	11.16
Vodafone	209.06	222.70	6.52
Idea	195.37	211.21	8.11
RCOM/RTL	83.50	0.19	-99.77
BSNL	100.99	111.68	10.59
Aircel	90.90	74.15	-18.43
Reliance JIO	108.68	186.56	71.66
Tata	48.99	31.19	-36.33
Telenor	50.49	37.98	-24.78
Sistema*	4.91	-	
MTNL	3.63	3.56	-1.93
Total	1170.18	1183.41	1.13

*The services of M/s Sistema Shyam Ltd. have been taken over by M/s RCOM/RTL in 2017-18

I. From Table 1 it is very clear that there has been a rise in the usage of mobile in the rural area at steady rate.

II. With the introduction of private companies in the communication sector, people have more awareness and usage of mobile and internet in the country (Table 2).

III. With the increase use of financial services through internet there has been increase in the number of companies which provide the platform to use these services.

IV. With the availability of Third-party companies and easy reach of mobile operators the subscriptions have increased from all the tables.

2)To highlight the initiatives taken by banks for promoting Digital Financial Services.

According to RBI “Mobile Banking in India is perhaps the biggest change in banking in recent times. The RBI issued its first set of regulatory guidelines to do with mobile banking in 2008, where banks were permitted to transfer funds from one bank account to another through the mobile platform. From 2010 to 2012, the number of users of mobile banking services grew 277.68% (from 5.96 million to 22.51 million) and the value grew a whopping 875.6% (from Rs. 6.14 billion to Rs. 59.90 billion). These figures clearly indicate that mobile banking in the country is growing at a very high rate. Yet, as of 2014, there were 350 to 500 million unique mobile subscribers. It is estimated to have the user base increased up to 800 million by the end of 2019 and only 22 million mobile banking customers.

The RBI clearly recognized the potential for a widespread increase in mobile banking as well as the opportunity of increasing financial inclusion in the country, and made recommendations for “addressing the consumer acquisition challenges as well as the technical aspects”. Recommendations such as alternate channels for mobile registration such as ATMs, uniformity in the mobile registration process across banks, and standardization and simplification of the MPIN generation process were made by the RBI. And with addition to its AADHAR CARD issuance and linking it with mobile phone was an appreciable move by the Prime Minister making clear, true and transparent information about the population of India and their lifestyle so whole in whole it is an excellent step taken up the Government of India. The individual can name a financial service and it is available in the digital form. Due to the customer satisfaction criteria taken up by the private as well as public sector, it is very easy for a customer as now the company reaches the customers.

Banking Initiatives to Encourage Digital Financial Services

To achieve speedy and prompt movement into the cashless, digital payments across all sectors of Indian economy and to encourage rapid adoption of digital payment systems based on user-friendly interface. The following digital financial services are currently being promoted across the country through banks.

Bank card - A bank card is typically a plastic card issued by a bank to its clients that performs one or more of a number of services that relate to giving the client access to funds, either from the client's own bank account, or through a credit account. It can also be a smart card. Physically, a bank card will usually have the client's name, the issuer's name, and a unique card number printed on it. It will have a magnetic strip on the back enabling various machines to read and access information. Depending on the issuing bank and the preferences of the client, this may allow the card to be used as an ATM card, enabling transactions at automatic teller machines; or as debit card, linked to the client's bank account and able to be used for making purchases at the point of sale; or as a credit card attached to a revolving credit line supplied by the bank.

□ **Bharat QR**- Bharat QR is the world's first interoperable Quick Response (QR) code acceptance solution developed by the payments industry to expedite India's transition to a less - cash society. It has been developed by National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI), Master card and Visa. Bharat QR was devised based on the direction set by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) in September 2016 and its Payments Vision 2018, which outlines innovation, interoperability, and security as the three pillars to facilitate India's transition to a less – cash society. The Bharat QR enables customers to transact money available in their bank accounts without having to worry about the physical availability of an active credit / debit card. Users will not need to scan different QR codes at the same merchant provided by the different payment networks.

□ **RuPay**- RuPay is a brand of NPCI under which it operates the card scheme. The National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI) is a pioneer organization in the field of retail payments in

India. It is a body promoted by RBI and has presently ten core promoter banks (State Bank of India, Punjab National Bank, Canara Bank, Bank of Baroda, Union Bank of India, Bank of India, ICICI Bank, HDFC Bank, Citibank and HSBC). The vision of NPCI being able to provide citizens of our country anytime, anywhere payment services which are simple, easy to use, safe, and secure, fast and also cost effective. NPCI aims to operate for the benefit of all the member banks and the common man at large.

□ **Virtual Credit Card-** A virtual credit card (VCC) is an exclusive online payment solution with complete online security while shopping on Internet. It is like an add-on card issued on the user's primary credit card. Virtual credit card is a one-time usable card which comes with a preloaded amount that is valid only for a specified time period. VCCs do not have any plastic or physical existence and they are created to be used only online. Also the virtual card does not have any fee associated with it. The key details of the virtual credit cards like the card number, expiry date, CVV number etc. are used when using the card online, but the user's primary card details are never shared with the merchant online. So, while using the virtual credit card online, users need not worry about losing their card or carrying their card safely in their wallet. Many banks offer virtual cards instantly these days.

Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD) channel

This service allows mobile banking transactions using basic feature mobile phone, there is no need to have mobile internet data facility for using USSD based mobile banking. It is envisioned to provide financial deepening and inclusion of under banked society in the mainstream banking services. *99# service has been launched to take the banking services to every common man across the country. Banking customers can avail this service by dialing *99#, a “Common number across all Telecom Service Providers (TSPs)” on their mobile phone and transact through an interactive menu displayed on the mobile screen. Key services offered under *99# service include, inter-bank account to account fund transfer, balance enquiry, mini statement besides host of other services. *99# service is currently offered by 51 leading banks & all GSM service providers and can be accessed in 12 different languages including Hindi & English as on 30.11.2016 (Source: NPCI). *99# service is a unique interoperable direct to consumer service that brings together the diverse ecosystem partners such as Banks & TSPs (Telecom Service Providers).

Aadhaar Enabled Payment System (AEPS)

Aadhaar Enabled Payment System provides basic financial services (cash deposit, balance enquiry, cash withdrawal and remittance) at low cost access devices (called Micro ATMs) maintained at Business correspondents in an inter-operable way.

The Aadhaar enabled basic types of banking transactions are:

- Cash Withdrawal
- Cash Deposit
- Aadhaar to Aadhaar Funds Transfer
- Balance Enquiry

□ Gateway Authentication Service

Unified Payments Interface (UPI): Unified Payments Interface (UPI) is a system that powers multiple bank accounts into a single mobile application (of any participating bank), merging several banking features, seamless fund routing & merchant payments into one hood. It also caters to the “Peer to Peer” collect request which can be scheduled and paid as per requirement and convenience. Each Bank provides its own UPI App for Android, Windows and iOS mobile platform(s).

E-wallets -E-wallet is a type of electronic card which is used for transactions made online through a computer or a smart phone. Its utility is same as a credit or debit card. An E-wallet needs to be linked with the individual’s bank account to make payments. E-wallet is a type of pre-paid account in which a user can store his/her money for any future online transaction. An E-wallet is protected with a password. With the help of an E-wallet, one can make payments for groceries, online purchases, and flight tickets, among others. E-wallet has mainly two components, software and information. The software component stores personal information and provides security and encryption of the data. The information component is a database of details provided by the user which includes their name, shipping address, payment method, amount to be paid, credit or debit card details, etc. For setting up an E-wallet account, the user needs to install the software on his/her device, and enter the relevant information required. After shopping online, the E-wallet automatically fills in the user’s information on the payment form. To activate the E-wallet, the user needs to enter his password. Once the online payment is made, the consumer is not required to fill the order form on any other website as the information gets stored in the database and is updated automatically.

The point of sale (POS) or point of purchase (POP) -The point of sale (POS) or point of purchase (POP) is the time and place where a retail transaction is completed. At the point of sale, the merchant calculates the amount owed by the customer, indicates that amount, may prepare an invoice for the customer (which may be a cash register printout), and indicates the options for the customer to make payment. It is also the point at which a customer makes a payment to the merchant in exchange for goods or after provision of a service. After receiving payment, the merchant may issue a receipt for the transaction, which is usually printed but is increasingly being dispensed with or sent electronically.

Online Banking: Internet banking, also known as online banking, e-banking or virtual banking, is an electronic payment system that enables customers of a bank or other financial institution to conduct a range of financial transactions through the financial institution's website. Broadly, the electronic banking transactions can be divided into two categories: (1) Remote / online payment transactions (transactions that do not require physical payment instruments to be presented at the point of transactions e.g. internet banking, mobile banking, card not present (CNP) transactions), Pre-paid Payment Instruments (PPI) and (2) Face-to-face/ proximity payment transactions

(transactions which require the physical payment instrument such as a card or mobile phone to be present at the point of transaction e.g. ATM, POS, etc.)

National Electronic Fund Transfer (NEFT)-National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT) is a nation-wide payment system facilitating one-to-one funds transfer. Under this Scheme, individuals, firms and corporates can electronically transfer funds from any bank branch to any individual, firm or corporate having an account with any other bank branch in the country participating in the Scheme. Individuals, firms or corporates maintaining accounts with a bank branch can transfer funds using NEFT. Even such individuals who do not have a bank account (walk-in customers) can also deposit cash at the NEFT-enabled branches with instructions to transfer funds using NEFT. However, such cash remittances will be restricted to a maximum of Rs. 50,000/- per transaction. NEFT, thus, facilitates originators or remitters to initiate funds transfer transactions even without having a bank account. Presently, NEFT operates in hourly batches - there are twelve settlements from 8 am to 7 pm on week days (Monday through Friday) and six settlements from 8 am to 1 pm on Saturdays.

Real Time Gross Settlement (RTGS)- RTGS is defined as the continuous (real-time) settlement of funds transfers individually on an order by order basis (without netting). 'Real Time' means the processing of instructions at the time they are received rather than at some later time: 'Gross Settlement' means the settlement of funds transfer instructions occurs individually (on an instruction by instruction basis). Considering that the funds settlement takes place in the books of the Reserve Bank of India, the payments are final and irrevocable. The RTGS system is primarily meant for large value transactions. The minimum amount to be remitted through RTGS is 2 lakhs. There is no upper ceiling for RTGS transactions. The RTGS service for customer's transactions is available to banks from 9.00 hours to 16.30 hours on week days and from 9.00 hours to 14:00 hours on Saturdays for settlement at the RBI end. However, the timings that the banks follow may vary depending on the customer timings of the bank branches.

Electronic Clearing System (ECS)- ECS is an alternative method for effecting payment transactions in respect of the utility-bill-payments such as telephone bills, electricity bills, insurance premium, card payments and loan repayments, etc., which would obviate the need for issuing and handling paper instruments and thereby facilitate improved customer service by banks / companies / corporation's / government departments, etc., collecting / receiving the payments.

Immediate Payment Service (IMPS)- IMPS is real-time remittance service available anytime, anywhere across India. Using IMPS customers can transfer money real-time to any person or to a merchant, for any personal or commercial purpose. IMPS is available round-the-clock and operates even during bank holiday, weekends or festive holidays. IMPS can be used on any platform - Mobile, Internet and ATM across any bank in India.

3) To link digital empowerment with the philosophy and practice of inclusive growth.

Digital Literacy and Inclusion

India faces the big problem of structural unemployment and underemployment, disguised unemployment improper trainer and worker relationship, and unequal distribution of wealth today. This is mainly because lack of digital illiteracy and shortage of soft skills in many places. Digital literacy is no longer a luxury but a necessity. It has the potential of significantly altering economic status, social relations and media.

The India Stack: A Multi-Stakeholder Approach to Digital Financial Inclusion. As part of the “Digital India Programme,” which was formally launched in July 2015, the Government of India embarked on several initiatives aimed at expanding the digital economy, including facilitating digital financial inclusion. Observers have dubbed the combination of the many technology initiatives undertaken by both Government and Non-Government stakeholders, including those pre dating the launch of the Digital India Programme, the “India Stack”. Core elements of the stack focus on generating greater efficiency in the delivery of G2P social transfers, e.g., subsidies and social cash transfers, as well as on removing barriers to financial access, including limited access to formal ID documentation, bank branches or agents, and to credit for micro-entrepreneurs and SMEs.

Elements of the India Stack

The India Stack is an open digital infrastructure platform that makes use of open Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) to promote “presence-less, paperless, and cashless delivery” of services across different sectors of the economy. The India Stack is built on four technology layers:

- 1) **Presence-less layer** which leverages India’s Aadhaar unique identification and authentication system to enable remote and real-time identification and verification of individuals and businesses
- 2) **Paper-less layer** which is comprised of a “Digital Locker” and “Digital Signature” (or e-Signature) and enables entities to share documents and enter into contracts digitally and remotely
- 3) **Cash-less layer** which is based on the recently developed Unified Payments Interface and which allows for real-time and interoperable payments across all bank accounts and mobile wallets. Transactions can be stored, and transaction histories shared, for example, with credit providers to enable alternative credit-scoring models
- 4) **Consent layer** which, while not yet complete, will enable individuals to share data of their choosing, or to allow time-bound and identity-verified access to their data, but only with their consent. While the India Stack is itself an innovative platform approach that can significantly expand access to digital financial services, it builds on the initiatives

undertaken by several Government departments, as well as by other public authorities and non-government stakeholders. Initiatives undertaken by the Government and other public authorities include:

- In 2009, the Unique Identification Authority of India (UIDAI) launched the Aadhaar ID scheme, which has provided a unique biometric identity to over 1 billion people. The ID scheme captures biometric information from individuals, including iris scans and thumbprints, and issues a unique 12-digit ID number to each individual.¹⁸ The UIDAI has also developed an e-KYC platform based on the Aadhaar ID database
- The Indian Software Product Industry Roundtable (iSPIRT), a non-governmental organization aimed at promoting the Indian software industry, was established in 2013 and has been instrumental in promoting the development of APIs and supporting systems for the India Stack.
- The Wireless in Local Loop (WLL) technology developed by IIT Chennai has helped in providing Internet connectivity to 250 community Kiosks that offers these services to over 700,00 people in rural India. But this is half the distance covered. Rather it is “ICT vehicle coming to the village” not the “villagers driving the ICT vehicle” to move away from poverty.

The coordinated cross-government approach taken to developing the foundations of the India Stack has not only resulted in a significant increase in the number of individuals with access to digital transaction accounts and other financial services as indicated above, but it has also enabled the Government to digitize the delivery of subsidies and social welfare payments, resulting in estimated savings of close to Rs 50 billion (USD 750 million) as of December 2016.

Authorities still face challenges, of course, in leveraging the India Stack for financial inclusion. For example, last-mile challenges of delivering services in rural/remote areas remain, with continuing low density of banking correspondent or agent networks. At the same time, newly-licensed MNO-led payment banks face challenges in re-orienting their agent networks, long used to providing airtime and SIM registration services, to providing financial services

CONCLUSION

Digital finance can lead to greater financial inclusion, expansion of financial services to non-financial sectors, and the expansion of basic services to individuals since nearly 50% of people in the developing world already own a mobile phone (World Bank, 2014). Digital financial inclusion has some benefits. Digital financial inclusion promises to help banks lower costs by reducing queuing lines in banking halls, reduce manual paperwork and documentation and to maintain fewer bank branches (IFC, 2017). With digital financial inclusion, large number of depositors can easily switch banks within minutes; forcing banks to provide quality services or risk losing depositors to rival banks. For financial and monetary system regulators, digital financial inclusion also helps to reduce the amount of physical cash in circulation and is instrumental in reducing high inflation levels in developing and poor countries (GPFI, 2016). Digital financial inclusion can improve the welfare of individuals and businesses that have a reliable digital platform with which to access funds in their bank accounts to carry out financial transactions (CGAP, 2015). The expected benefits of digital financial inclusion can be fully realized if the cost of obtaining a digital transactional platform by poor individuals is negligible or low, where a digital transactional platform refers to mobile phones, personal computers and related devices.

Accessibility to digital technology and accomplishment/impact of digital empowerment offers the researcher a broad spectrum of methodological investigation, taking into account the critical conceptual and practical aspects therein. There is no easy route to digital empowerment. Further the methodological approach keeps evolving and has to adapt to the changing functional, technological and human perspectives of growth in general and inclusive growth in particular. Therefore, it is wise to blend technological and human approaches that strengthen the enabling and evaluatory mechanisms of digital empowerment.

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